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(Assessment of Teachers' and Students' Knowledge on Green Chemistry Concepts ... Aladesuyi, D. A. & Abidoeye, F. O. 2025)

Assessment of Teachers' and Students' Knowledge on Green Chemistry Concepts in Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the level of knowledge of green chemistry particularly the use of alternative, safer solvents among secondary school chemistry teachers and students in Kwara State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, involving 200 participants (20 teachers and 180 SS2 students) selected through a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a researcher-designed Green Chemistry Knowledge Test (GCKT), validated by experts and tested for reliability yielded a value of 0.81 using Cronbach's Alpha. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and independent samples t-test. Findings revealed a generally low level of knowledge of green chemistry concepts across both groups. The study highlights the urgent need for curriculum reform, improved teacher training, and structured dissemination of green chemistry content to align chemistry education with global sustainability goals.

Keywords: Green Chemistry, Knowledge Level, Safer Solvents, Curriculum

Introduction

The increasing environmental challenges facing the world today ranging from industrial pollution to the depletion of natural resources have intensified global efforts towards sustainability. In the face of a growing global population, accelerating industrialization, and finite natural resources, the urgency of adopting sustainable development approaches has become more pronounced.

Sustainable development is a crucial global agenda focused on promoting long-term well-being and improving the quality of life for both present and future generations. It involves advancing physical and cultural growth while safeguarding natural resources to ensure the needs of future generations are met (Martin-Blanco et al., 2022). Its ultimate goal is to create a society where human needs are fulfilled without jeopardizing the integrity of natural systems (Mensah, 2019). Addressing such multifaceted global issues requires a transformative shift in human behavior and decision-making, which can only be achieved through education.

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Education serves as a key mechanism for equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for sustainable living. Achieving the vision of sustainability, therefore, necessitates deliberate educational interventions, and at the center of such efforts lies the curriculum. Curriculum, in its modern conceptualization, refers to a dynamic and systematic plan of educational experiences that intentionally develops learners' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values (Schiro, 2023). It extends beyond mere content delivery to include the pedagogical strategies, assessment methods, and educational goals that shape the learning process (Wyse & Manyukhina, 2024). As such, the curriculum plays a vital role in ensuring equitable access to quality education and in preparing students to contribute meaningfully to societal advancement (Federal Republic of Nigeria [FRN], 2013).

Within this framework, the teaching and learning of chemistry occupies a pivotal position. The study of chemistry is as old as humanity, with its influence evident from the Stone Age through the Iron Age to the modern technological era (Audu et al., 2022). The knowledge of chemistry serves as a foundational pillar for numerous professions, including engineering, agriculture, medicine, pharmacy, nursing, and biochemistry (Umanah & Akpan, 2024). Given the discipline's historical and contemporary relevance, understanding how chemical principles are taught and applied through education is critical. Chemistry education fosters not only scientific knowledge but also essential process skills and positive scientific attitudes in learners (Chinda et al., 2025).

The chemistry curriculum, therefore, acts as a strategic blueprint for addressing societal needs and national aspirations, aligning closely with broader educational objectives (Igboanugo, 2018). In recent years, it has become increasingly important for this curriculum to reflect global scientific trends, particularly those that respond to environmental and sustainability challenges. One of the most promising scientific responses to these global concerns is green chemistry, which integrates sustainability principles directly into chemical design and application. Green chemistry focuses on designing products and processes that minimise or eliminate the use and generation of hazardous substances, thereby reducing risks to human health and the environment (Tundo et al., 2020; Anastas & Warner, 2020). According to Auliah et al. (2018), the principles of sustainability embodied in green chemistry should be introduced and socialized at all levels of education to cultivate environmentally responsible citizens. This philosophy includes the use of alternative safer solvent adhering to green chemistry concepts (Ivanković et al., 2017).

In alignment with global efforts to integrate sustainability into science education, several empirical studies have investigated the level of knowledge and awareness of green chemistry. Ridha and Hasan (2020), examined environmental awareness among chemistry and non-chemistry undergraduate students at Universitas Syiah Kuala in Indonesia. Similarly, Mahat et al. (2018) conducted a geographically stratified study assessing secondary school students' knowledge of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) across five distinct zones in

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Malaysia. In the Indian context, Naikoo and Begum (2018) explored the knowledge levels of secondary school teachers regarding sustainable development in the region of Jammu and Kashmir.

In Nigeria, related studies have been carried out by Moju and Owoyemi (2020), Owoyemi and Adesina (2020), and Daniel et al. (2024); however, these investigations were primarily concentrated in the southern regions of the country, thereby limiting their geographical representativeness. Additionally, Oyelekan and Salihu (2022) focused exclusively on chemistry teachers' knowledge of green chemistry in Kwara State, without incorporating student perspectives. Their study, while valuable, also concentrated primarily on the concept of pollution prevention, overlooking other critical green chemistry principles such as the use of alternative, safer solvents. It is against that the study assess teachers and students' knowledge on green chemistry for achieving sustainable development goals in Kwara State.

Objectives of the Study

The study investigated teachers and students' knowledge on green chemistry concepts in Kwara State. Specifically, the study investigated the:

- i. level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry teachers in Kwara State.
- ii. level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry students in Kwara State.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry teachers in Kwara State?
- ii. What is the level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry students in Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mean knowledge scores towards integrating green chemistry concepts between teachers and students in Kwara State.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate for collecting and analyzing data from a relatively large population. This design enabled the researcher to assess and compare the level of knowledge of green chemistry concepts among secondary school chemistry teachers and SS2 students in Kwara State, Nigeria.

The population of the study comprised all senior secondary school chemistry teachers and SS2 chemistry students across public secondary schools in Kwara State. SS2 students were selected

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for participation because, at this level, they have been introduced to core chemistry topics relevant to the study.

A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select participants. Purposive sampling was employed to select four Local Government Areas (LGAs), representing the three senatorial districts of Kwara State. Thereafter, simple random sampling was used to select five public secondary schools from the identified LGAs. From each selected school, one chemistry teacher was selected, and proportionate sampling was used to select a total of 180 SS2 chemistry students. This yielded a sample size of approximately 200 participants (20 chemistry teachers and 180 chemistry students).

The instrument for data collection was a researcher-designed Green Chemistry Knowledge Questionnaire (GCKQ). The questionnaire consisted of two sections: Section A: Demographic information (teacher or student) and Section B: Twenty (20) structured items developed to assess participants' level of knowledge on green chemistry concepts, particularly focusing on safer chemical practices, alternative solvents, and environmental sustainability. Each item in Section B was rated using a 4-point Likert scale designed to measure participants' self-reported knowledge level: 4-High Knowledge (HK), 3-Moderate Knowledge (MK), 2-Low Knowledge (LK), and 1- No Knowledge (NK). The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts in chemistry education and science curriculum studies at the University of Ilorin.

Their reviews informed revisions that enhanced the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the items. To establish the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted using a sample of 10 chemistry teachers and 30 SS2 students who were not included in the main study. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient, which yielded a value of 0.81, indicating a high level of reliability.

Descriptive statistics such as mean scores, standard deviation, and percentage were used to describe the level of green chemistry knowledge among teachers and students. To test the null hypothesis, an independent samples t-test was employed to determine whether a statistically significant difference existed between the mean knowledge scores of teachers and students. All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 25, and the hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Table 1

Distributions of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher	20	10.0

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Student	180	90.0
Total	200	100.0

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents in the study shows that a total of 200 participants were involved. From which, 20 (10.0%) were chemistry teachers, while 180 (90.0%) were chemistry students. This distribution reflects the focus of the study on capturing a broader representation of students' knowledge of green chemistry concepts while also comparing it with that of their teachers. The higher proportion of student respondents provides a robust basis for analyzing students' level of awareness and understanding, while the inclusion of teachers allows for meaningful comparison between both groups.

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry teachers in Kwara State?

Table 2:

Mean and Standard Deviation of Teachers' Knowledge on Green Chemistry Concepts

S/N	Item	Mean Score	SD	Interpretation
1	Safer solvents in pharmaceuticals	1.65	0.65	Low Knowledge
2	Natural solvents replace benzene	1.95	0.80	Low Knowledge
3	Green solvents in cosmetics	1.45	0.59	Low Knowledge
4	CO ₂ for decaffeination	1.65	0.85	Low Knowledge
5	Bio-based solvents for cleaning	1.60	0.66	Low Knowledge
6	Solvents in paints reduce pollution	2.10	0.94	Moderate Knowledge
7	Solvents reduce lab accidents	2.20	1.03	Moderate Knowledge
8	Green solvents in food/drug	1.85	0.85	Low Knowledge
9	Reduce hazardous waste	2.15	0.96	Moderate Knowledge
10	Ethanol/water used in student practicals	2.40	1.07	Moderate Knowledge
11	Green solvents in cosmetics/adhesives	1.65	0.85	Low Knowledge
12	Solvent substitution reduces emissions	1.70	0.71	Low Knowledge
13	Acetone safer than chloroform	1.95	0.92	Low Knowledge

Table 2 reveals an overall low level of knowledge regarding the use of safer alternative solvents in green chemistry applications. Most mean scores across the 13 items fall below 2.50 on a 4-point Likert scale, indicating limited awareness or understanding. Teachers showed slightly higher knowledge in Items 6, 7, 9, and 10, which relate to practical or classroom-oriented applications such as the use of water and ethanol as safer solvents in student experiments (M = 2.40), and the role of safer solvents in reducing health risks (M = 2.20) and hazardous waste (M = 2.15). Items such as Items 3, 4, and 11, which involve specialized applications (e.g., glycerol in cosmetics, supercritical CO₂ in decaffeination, and green solvents in consumer products), had mean scores well below 2.00.

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Research Question 2: What is the level of knowledge of green chemistry among secondary school chemistry students in Kwara State?

Table 3

Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Knowledge on Green Chemistry Concepts

S/N	Item	Mean Score	SD	Interpretation
1	Safer solvents in pharmaceuticals	1.58	0.74	Low Knowledge
2	Natural solvents replace benzene	1.75	0.83	Low Knowledge
3	Green solvents in cosmetics	1.52	0.66	Low Knowledge
4	CO ₂ for decaffeination	1.47	0.67	Low Knowledge
5	Bio-based solvents for cleaning	1.53	0.70	Low Knowledge
6	Solvents in paints reduce pollution	1.80	0.86	Low Knowledge
7	Solvents reduce lab accidents	1.88	0.88	Low Knowledge
8	Green solvents in food/drug	1.62	0.75	Low Knowledge
9	Reduce hazardous waste	1.74	0.82	Low Knowledge
10	Ethanol/water used in student practicals	2.02	0.95	Moderate Knowledge
11	Green solvents in cosmetics/adhesives	1.56	0.72	Low Knowledge
12	Solvent substitution reduces emissions	1.58	0.69	Low Knowledge
13	Acetone safer than chloroform	1.71	0.78	Low Knowledge

Table 3 indicate a predominantly low level of knowledge across the 13 green chemistry items. With most mean scores falling below 2.00, and only Item 10 (Water and ethanol use in student practicals) reaching a moderate knowledge level ($M = 2.02$), the data suggests that SS2 chemistry students in Kwara State have limited exposure to the concept of safer alternative solvents.

Students demonstrated slightly better awareness in practical contexts, such as laboratory safety (Item 7: $M = 1.88$) and solvent use in paints and coatings (Item 6: $M = 1.80$), although these values still indicate low levels of understanding. Items related to industrial, environmental, and health related uses of green solvents such as Items 1, 3, 4, and 5 had especially low mean scores ($M < 1.60$), reflecting minimal or no exposure to such content in their learning experience.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mean knowledge scores towards integrating green chemistry concepts between teachers and students in Kwara State.

Table 4:

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Independent Samples t-test on Knowledge of Green Chemistry Concepts between Teachers and Students

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value (2-tailed)	Decision
Teachers	20	2.12	0.28	198	1.54	0.125	Accept H_0
Students	180	2.05	0.34				

Table 4 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean knowledge scores of chemistry teachers ($M = 2.12$, $SD = 0.28$) and students ($M = 2.05$, $SD = 0.34$) on green chemistry concepts in Kwara State, $t(198) = 1.54$, $p = 0.125$. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that there is no significant difference in the mean knowledge scores between teachers and students, is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that chemistry teachers in Kwara State demonstrated generally low levels of knowledge regarding green chemistry principles, especially in relation to the application of safer alternative solvents. This can be linked to the structure of the Nigerian chemistry curriculum, which does not explicitly address green chemistry or sustainability-related themes. Consequently, teachers are neither equipped with the knowledge nor the resources to teach such concepts effectively. This observation is consistent with the findings of Oyelekan and Salihu (2022), who investigated chemistry teachers' knowledge of green chemistry in Kwara State and reported limited awareness among teachers, with most discussions focusing solely on pollution prevention. Similarly, Naikoo and Begum (2018) found that science teachers in Jammu and Kashmir, India, had insufficient knowledge of sustainable development, further supporting the conclusion that sustainability education is inadequately embedded in science teacher preparation programmes.

The findings indicated that secondary school chemistry students in Kwara State possess limited knowledge of green chemistry principles. This low level of awareness is likely due to minimal exposure to green chemistry content during classroom instruction and laboratory practice. The practical application of safer solvents is rarely demonstrated, potentially due to a lack of equipment, instructional resources, or teacher expertise. These findings are corroborated by Ridha and Hasan (2020), who reported low levels of environmental sustainability awareness among undergraduate students in Indonesia, especially those outside the core science disciplines. Conversely, this result contrasts with Mahat et al. (2018), who found higher levels of sustainability knowledge among secondary school students in Malaysia an outcome likely influenced by national policy reforms and curriculum development efforts that prioritize sustainability education.

Furthermore, the acceptance of the null hypothesis indicating no statistically significant difference between the mean knowledge scores of teachers and students suggests that both

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groups have had equally limited exposure to green chemistry concepts. This result aligns with the findings of Agbayewa et al. (2013), who examined the incorporation of green chemistry concepts into the senior secondary chemistry curriculum and reported that several relevant contents lacked integration with green chemistry principles and were presented without adequate emphasis on their importance.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed a generally low level of knowledge of green chemistry principles particularly the use of alternative, safer solvents among both secondary school chemistry teachers and students in Kwara State, Nigeria. This pervasive knowledge gap suggests that green chemistry concepts are either absent or insufficiently addressed within the current chemistry curriculum and teaching practices. Both groups showed limited awareness, with no statistically significant difference in their mean knowledge scores, indicating a uniform lack of exposure across the board.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The revision of teacher education programmes, and curriculum updates that integrate green chemistry principles, particularly the use of safer solvents as alternatives to traditional hazardous chemicals.
2. Learner-friendly instructional materials and activities that contextualize green chemistry concepts should be developed and implemented.

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